

Indian Elections: An inclusive study of ‘Money’ & ‘Muscle’ power

Rohil

Research Scholar, Centre for Study of Social Exclusion & Inclusive Policy, Panjab University, Chandigarh.

E-mail: rohil1991@gmail.com

Abstract

Being the largest democracy of the world, India has presented itself as an example of nurturing a democracy. But in spite of that, the democracy has not been realized up to the full extent because of certain issues rooted in the exercise of its Elections. Here, the researcher has tried to indicate the most important and integral happenings in the present day electoral system under two broad categories viz. money power and muscle power. This is to say that all the issues pertaining to the elections in India have somehow, the root cause as either of the two powers titled above. Some of these issues have been regulated by the Honorable Supreme Court of India and the Election Commission of India, in the past such as invoking communalism in elections, opinion polls, spending limits, paid news, vote purchasing, use of Government machinery, criminalization, etc. But there are still some issues which are difficult to eliminate and even not got much breakthrough in the Courts and by the Commission, in the name of individual rights & liberty and Directive Principles, such as regulation of the political parties under Right to Information Act, the announcement of freebies in the manifestos, corporate financing of the Elections, horse trading, etc. This paper tries to discuss the various manifestations (covering all the election issues) of money and muscle used as power to win the elections and the steps taken by the Government.

Keywords: Election issues, criminalization of politics, money power, electoral challenges in India, electoral reforms, electoral violence

Introduction

India is one among the largest Democracies of the World. The Elections form a basic component of Politics in a Democratic system. Elections are held as a process of legitimization of the political power to be acquired (Singh, 2013). In this dynamic scenario, for safeguarding the core values of the free and fair elections, it is important to have a just and unbiased electoral process to ensure greater citizen participation. However, there are certain challenges and issues that electoral system have faced over the years. Trust and confidence of the citizens in electoral system cannot be gained without addressing these issues (Election Commission of India, 2016). A discernible decline in the standards began and the distortion in its working appeared for the first time in the fifth General Elections in 1971 which multiplied in the subsequent elections. The Election process in our country is the root cause of the political corruption. The issue of Election reforms has been taken up by the Parliament, the Government, the Judiciary, the Media and the Election Commission on the numerous occasions but it needs to be corrected at the societal level itself through education and awareness.

The major roadblocks in the path of Indian Electoral system are broadly categorized by the researcher under two categories as: Money power and Muscle power.

Money Power

It plays a destructive role in our electoral system affecting seriously the working of periodic elections. It leads to all round corruption and contribute majorly towards the generation of black money economy. Almost all the major issues pertaining to the elections in India are influenced by the power of money. The money remains the powerful instrument from the very beginning of the electoral process.

Rich Candidate

In the very first instance, the tickets are provided to the wealthy candidates who can self finance the election. According to Sircar (2018), “ In the 2014 national elections, candidates reported a median wealth of Rs 23.8 lakhs--approximately 27 times the nominal per capita income of India in 2014-15 of Rs 88,533- which is, in turn significantly wealthier than the general population.” If the candidates contesting the elections need to be wealthy, then only a small section of the population will be eligible to hold the office, which will result in the representatives that have less in common with the citizens they represent. Second, if parties increasingly rely upon the ‘wealth’ rather than ‘education’ or ‘social service’ as criteria to select candidates, then the elected representatives may become worse at representing their constituents. Last but not the least, self financing candidates may view elections as investment which will increase their chances of being corrupt in office and will try to recover the costs of contesting elections. To sum up we can say that the root cause of rise in affluent candidates is the weak representative role of India’s elected politicians because the policymaking power is restricted to the small set of party elites (**Sircar, 2018**).

Expensive campaigns

Secondly, the candidates have to spend millions of money towards transport, publicity (rallies and processions) and other essential items of election campaigns (table, chairs, posters, flags, etc). Yet the actual spending by him/her remains unclear due to the paucity of credible data on actual expenses. However, gifts are not the prime reason for expensive elections but many other expenses, from basic logistical costs to the short term wages that candidates pay to the workers and the crowds recruited by them (termed as “paid political participation” by the political scientists), place more constraints on candidates (**Chauchard, 2018**). These payments cannot be equated with bribes as the wages are traded to poor people for work (such as carrying flags and seating idly on plastic chairs), and not for votes. Apart from this, the other reasons for expensive elections are: (i) Increase in the size of the constituency as for larger population, the candidates have to spend more. (ii) generational changes which means that there is a rise in number of young educated voters who are not easily get into the rhetoric and are independent of family’s partisan orientation. (iii) Steady rise in the political competitions and hence costlier contests to match the expenses of the competitors.

Elections funding

The survey on 2577 politicians in the states of Bihar, UP and Jharkhand, done by Bussells (2018), pointed out the perceived sources of income of candidates to be spent on elections as- personal income, party funds, company donations, individual donations, funds from bureaucrats and black money. It further stated that more than 60% politicians at state and national level reported support from party funds in contrast to panchayat and district level politicians who are reliant on help from local organizations. Survey evidence from North India shows that “the politicians from Panchayat level to the Member of Parliament are highly reliant on their own sources. Private sector funding usually complements a candidate’s own finances, especially at the state and national levels.” The investigations done by Kapur & Vaishnav (2018) reveal that “much of the action is at what TN Ninan calls the “mezzanine level” -- medium-sized firms and businessmen who are reliant on routine government clearances. Evidence suggested that politicians help real

estate builders negotiate the complex system of regulatory approvals dealing with land in exchange for cash infusions during elections time.”

According to the Survey discussed above, when the politicians were asked about the most important source of funds for their peers, the most common response by the national and state politicians was the funds accumulated through corrupt means (Black money). If this is the case, then it is understood that one who has the ability to provide illicit sources of funds to a candidate during elections, will also exercise more influence over the elected official.

Vote purchasing

The support by various actors (discussed above) for financing the election campaign is the help in purchasing the votes by distributing handouts and gifts to the voters on the eve of the Election Day. “The more accurate term for the pre election distribution is gift giving rather than vote buying (rational strategy when a candidate seeks to boost her own credibility or to simply match what other rivals are doing) which over time has created an electoral finance arms race. While it is technically illegal but it is reported that candidates are pressurized to distribute gifts on the campaign trail” (Kapur & Vaishnav, 2018). “From saris to cycles, there have always been stories of the generous handouts Indian political campaigners use to bribe voters. These can also range from cash—Rs 1000 to Rs 2500 per vote, wheat packets, liquor to a free *biryani*, a night before the elections. As the focus on corruption has increased, the campaigners have resorted to some new ways of vote buying. It has been found that people handing out coupons which can be exchanged for a bottle of liquor or Rs 10 notes of a specific serial number, which stores recognize and swap for a bottle or wheat packet wherever applicable” (Chilkoti, 2014).

Freebies

The freebies are the gifts or sops announced in the manifestos of the political parties that have no other purpose than to induce voters to vote for a particular party. It all started with the late MG Ramchandran (MGR) distributing free dhotis and saris. The high time in freebies culture was in the 2006 when DMK promised a free color TV to each and every household not possessing it. In 2011 elections Jayalalithaa’s AIADMK in its manifesto promised freebies worth more than Rs 9000 cr. which included laptops, mixer grinders & table fans, cash & gold to poor girls at the time of their marriage, green houses to poor farmers, free rice, free cows & goats to the poor families in selected rural areas, etc (Datar, 2019, p.12). Earlier, this culture was limited to the southern Indian states but recently it has been increasingly used as strategy to woo voters by the political parties in Northern states too as Samajwadi Party in Uttar Pradesh fulfilled the promised laptops and the smart phones were promised by the Congress party in Punjab. Due to inability to deliver on good governance, the only way for political parties to impress frustrated voters is to promise them more and more freebies in each succeeding election. These freebies and loan waivers will eventually bankrupt state after state but that’s just a small price for the nation to pay for ensuring ‘free and fair elections’.

This was all the discussion about the manifestation of the money power in the electoral system of India according to the researcher. Let us discuss the other part of this paper about the manifestations of the

Muscle Power

Criminalization

“There is a clear nexus between crime and politics in India fueled by two set of factors. First, parties are desperate to identify candidates with deep pockets (as discussed earlier) which have led them to embrace wealthy individuals with often dubious reputations. Second, voters have their own reasons to support

candidates with questionable background. Where government is unable to fulfill its basic responsibilities and social divisions are rife, voters seek refuge in strongmen who can deliver what the state cannot” (Vaishnav, 2017). They are able to use their criminality as a sign of their credibility to do whatever it takes—by hook or crook, to protect the status of the communities they claim to represent. In both the previous as well as present Lok Sabha, almost 30% of the members have one or more criminal cases registered against them for heinous offences such as murder, attempt to murder, extortion, rape, dacoity and kidnapping. It was found on enquiring that the actual percentage of criminality was higher because many cases had been settled in favor of the local musclemen/politicians by some way or the other. Till 1980’s many mafias would support candidates from outside with the hope of getting their interests fulfilled upon his victory. “It was only a matter of time before they decided that they were better off contesting elections themselves” (Chawla, 2017).

Electoral violence

The elections are a contest for power and can often lead to violence, intimidation and conflict to influence the results or timing of an election. This is specifically true when a particular side perceives the process as unfair or exclusive. Criminalization is not merely criminals contesting elections but resorting to criminal methods such as threat, intimidation and inducement, etc to win an election. In transitional countries, it is believed that the incumbents are manipulating or tampering with the election processes resulting in furthering of strength by opposition parties by resorting to violence. The consequences of electoral violence are - low voter registration and turnout, prevent candidates from running for offices, increased divisions in society, or sometimes postpone an election or prevent it from taking place. Three main forms of electoral violence include—

- (i) Acts of physical harm, assaults & attacks on communities or candidates, gender based violence, mob violence and political assassinations during campaign.
- (ii) Violent acts can be targeted against objects, buildings and structures as well as people, e.g. destruction of campaign material, vehicles, offices or ballot boxes.
- (iii) Threats and intimidation to the associated people, government servants and employees (for their transfers), small local businessmen and corporate.

Thus, as per Kumar (2015), “the election related conflict has devastated effects on the governance and development. When such violence occurs, it often impairs the functioning of the government institutions that emerge from processes where violence has tainted the fairness of the process and the legitimacy of election results.”

Caste Politics

Caste has been made an object of political mobilization by political parties in their quest for political support and votes. While the parties sought to exploit the caste for its own purposes, the caste groups using politics got a chance to assert their identity and bargain for benefits and position in society. All the political parties tend to choose candidate from amongst the numerically or otherwise dominant caste in every constituency. The major caste groups get representation in the council of ministers. In this way, the muscle power is exercised through caste based politics by the political parties.

Steps taken by the Governments

The various steps have been taken by the various governments from time to time yet the problems discussed, remaining to be as critical and challenging as ever. The joint Parliamentary Committee on Amendments to Election Law (1971-72), the Tarkunde Committee Report (1975), Goswami Committee Report (1990), Vohra Committee Report (1993), the Election Commission’s recommendations and Indrajit

Gupta Committee on State funding of Elections(1998), Law Commission's report on Reform of the Electoral Laws (1999),

National Commission to Review the working of the Constitution (2001), Election commission of India-proposed Electoral Reforms (2004), the Second Administrative Reforms Commission (2008), Law Commission Report on Electoral Reforms (2015), Election Commission of India-proposed Electoral Reforms (2016), etc produced a comprehensive set of recommendations regarding electoral reforms (**Ekka, 2018**).

But the issues discussed above have not found much remedial measures in these steps. There is a pervasive feeling among the people that something is wrong with the way elections are conducted in India. Keeping in mind the centrality of elections in renewing the legitimacy of the democratic political system it is expected that the distortions adversely affecting the conduct of free and fair elections, will be controlled and eliminated if by nothing else, than, at least, by making suitable changes in the law governing the conduct of elections. Now, time has come to provide some hard rules and laws in our constitution to keep away those anti-social evils from legislative institutions.

Suggestions

The following suggestions can be taken into consideration to control the discussed issues:

- The distribution of the tickets and filing nominations by the candidates should be done at least 3-4 months before the elections so that the complete verification of all the candidates would be done by the election commission itself regarding all the aspects discussed such as property (movable and immovable), income sources, verification for criminal cases, social verification (pilot study to know about the candidate from his/her constituency), etc. in addition to the affidavit filed by the candidate.
- Political Corruption should be stopped by providing funds to the genuine candidates through state funding of elections but before that the Election Commission has to ensure the transparency of the political parties (internal structure, funding, accounts, etc.)
- The affidavit filed by the candidate should also be verified by the respective political party. Any candidate involved in corruption & violence (directly or indirectly) should be disqualified and the respective political party should be deregistered and derecognized forthwith.
- There should be ceiling on spending by the political parties.
- Strict application of Model Code of Conduct and punishment for violation.
- Prompt action by the judiciary, if any kind of violation is detected during elections.
- Mass Media should play a non partisan role in elections and act as a safeguard of Democracy.

To conclude, we can say that the public is the most powerful entity in a democratic system. If the public do not vote in favor of criminals, dishonest persons and corrupt politicians, then the true essence of the democracy can be realized. The Election Commission is working hard in this direction but the people of India should also understand their responsibility to reform the electoral system of India.

REFERENCES

- Bussell, J. (2018, July 24). Funding elections in India: Whose money has the most influence? *Hindustan Times*. Retrieved from <http://www.hindustantimes.com>
- Chauchard, S. (2018, July 25). Why are elections getting more expensive in India? *Hindustan Times*. Retrieved from <http://www.hindustantimes.com>
- Chawla, N.B (2017, December 26). The unholy alliance of Muscle power and Money power is weakening Indian Democracy. *Hindustan Times*. Retrieved from <http://www.hindustantimes.com>
- Chilkoti, A. (2014, May 6). India elections: A festival of vote buying. *Financial Times*. Retrieved from <http://www.ft.com>
- Datar, A.P. (2019, January 5). Free for all voters. *The Indian Express*, p.12
- Ekka, N. (2018). “Electoral Reforms in India- Issues and Reforms”. Proceedings of the Conference on “Electoral Politics in North-East India: Analysis of 2018 Assembly Elections”, ICSSR-NERC, Shillong: Meghalaya, India. Retrieved from <http://www.adrindia.org>
- Election Commission of India, Proposed Electoral Reforms, New Delhi: Nirwahan Sadan, 2016
- Kapur, D. & Vaishnav, M. (2018, July 23). Power to the rich: India needs to talk about money in politics. *Hindustan Times*. Retrieved from <http://www.hindustantimes.com>
- Kumar, C. (2015). “Electoral Violence, Threats and Security: Problems and Prospects for Indian Democracy.” *American Journal of Social Science Research*, 1(1), 38-51. Retrieved from files.aiscience.org/journal/article/pdf/70330007.
- Singh, B.P. (2013). “Electoral Reforms in India- Issues and Challenges.” *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention*, 2(3), 1-5. Retrieved from [http://www.ijhssi.org/papers/v2\(3\)/version-2/A230105](http://www.ijhssi.org/papers/v2(3)/version-2/A230105)
- Sircar, N. (2018, July 26). Money matters in Indian elections: Why parties depend on wealthy candidates? *Hindustan Times*. Retrieved from <http://www.hindustantimes.com>
- Vaishnav, M. (2017). *When Crime Pays. Money and Muscle in Indian Politics*, India: HarperCollins.